

Table 2. Young and old plants as preferred hosts of golden apple snail. IRRI, 1987.

Plant species	Plants consumed (%) 48 h after infestation ^a	
	Young	Old
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	93 a	54 b
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	18 a	15 b
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	77 a	6 b
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	68 a	58 b
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	59 a	27 b
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i>	50 a	32 b
<i>Pistia stratiotes</i>	28 a	24 b
<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i>	6 a	1 b

^aAv of 5 replications. In a row, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Each female (4-5 cm height) was given 0.5 g of each test weed species (20- to 30-d-old) on 29-cm-diam GI sheet trays covered with mylar film cages. The setup had 10 replications. The amount consumed by the snails is shown in Table 1.

In a separate experiment, 7 g each of 2 weed stages (20- to 30-d-old and more than 40-d-old) were placed on each GI sheet tray and infested with 2 golden apple snails/ tray. The experiment had 5 replications. The amounts consumed by the snails were compared (Table 2).

Golden apple snails appear to have a wide host range and to feed on almost all lowland weeds. They prefer the soft, young parts of the plant. □

Single-dose anticoagulants for rodent control in irrigated ricefields

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We tested two singledose anticoagulants—bromadiolone and brodifacoum—to establish the appropriate time for rodent poison baiting.

Of 15 rodent species of economic importance in India, *Bandicota bengalensis*, *Rattus meltda*, and field mice *Mus* spp. cause huge rice crop losses in northern India. At early stages

Rodent activity (%)

1. Exposure of 0.005% bromadiolone bai at different weeks after transplanting. Arrows indicate time of poison baiting. Treatment at a) 4 WT, b) 6 WT, c) 8 WT, d) 10 WT, e) 12 WT, f) multiple baiting, g) continuous baiting in bamboo bait stations, h) activity in reference fields.

of rice growth, the rodents are confined to bunds and adjacent permanent pathways. They migrate inside the fields at crop maturity. As much as 12% tiller

damage by rodents was assessed in reference fields.

Treatment for rodents on bunds and adjacent pathways at 8-10 wk after

2. Exposure of 0.005% ready-to-use brodifacoum wax blocks at different weeks after transplanting. Arrows indicate time of poison baiting. Treatment at a) 4 WT, b) 6 WT, c) 8 WT, d) 10 WT, e) 12 WT, f) multiple baiting, g) activity in reference fields.

transplanting (WT) with 0.005% bromadiolone bait or 0.005% ready-to-use brodifacoum wax blocks resulted in maximum kill and 70-80% reduction in preharvest tiller cut damage (Fig. 1, 2). Poison baiting at 4 WT or 6 WT with either anticoagulant also was effective in killing rodents.

A large-scale immigration of rodents from surrounding areas near crop maturity resulted in high preharvest tiller damage. Treatment at 12 WT was not effective. Intake of poison bait declined significantly because of the availability of maturing rice grains.

Multiple poison baiting of rodents

with 0.005% bromadiolone or 0.005% brodifacoum baits at 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 WT was most effective in killing existing and immigrating rodent populations.

Bamboo bait stations were used for poison baiting during rainy days. Early consumption of 0.005% bromadiolone bait from these bamboo bait stations was substantial, resulting in high decline in rodent populations, but consumption declined considerably 10 WT. □

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Grain loss due to rat damage

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Of the known pests, the field rat *Bandicota bengalensis* causes substantial losses to the rice crop from sowing to harvest in Haryana.

We surveyed 171 fields in 11 villages of 4 blocks of Kurukshetra district, where mainly Jaya, PR106, and IR8 varieties are grown, from August to harvest in 1984. Maximum damage occurred at tillering and heading stages; tillers were cut 10-15 cm from the ground. The number of rat burrows varied from 2 to 13/field (0.4 ha), and they were confined to field boundaries. Cut tillers were found 5-15 m away from the burrows.

From field samples, we assessed yield losses caused by rats by taking the yield corresponding to the number of cut tillers/m² and the yield of healthy tillers/m². Cut tillers/m² varied from 5.2 to 47.5, grain yield losses ranged from 33.8 to 308.8 g/m². That can be estimated as 0.4 to 3.1 t/ha for Jaya, 0.6 to 1.9 t/ha for PR106, and 0.4 t/ha for IR8 (see table). Rats showed no varietal preference. The yield loss differences among varieties may be due to variations in size of the rat population in different villages. □